

FUNCTIONALIZED NANOCARBON BASED NANOCOMPOSITES AND ITS FEASIBLE APPLICATION AT LEO SPACE ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Recent advances in the development of nanocarbons (including carbon nanotube, graphene and their assembly) have gained much interest in the aerospace field. This study attempted the functionalization of graphene oxide/CNTs with organosilane in order to generate compatibility with a polymer matrices and to improve resistant to carbon materials against AO attack in the LEO space environment. Functionalized nanocarbon filled nanocomposites were prepared by using solution blending methods. To simulate the aging of nanocomposites under LEO space environments, an accelerating LEO space environment simulating equipment was used. Characterization of the nanocomposites after aging was discussed using the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, mass loss, and tensile test.

1 INTRODUCTION

The expansion of the space industry and increase of its economic value has led to the intensification of competition in terms of development costs because of the significant budget necessary for the space industry. Accordingly, weight reduction of space structures like satellites is a critical mission. In this regard, various materials are researched as potential space structure materials. In the case of polymer based composite materials, they are increasingly adopted as space structural materials due to their high specific strength. However, hazardous environments exist in the low earth orbit environment, where most satellites are operated, that can be critical to polymer materials widely used as the matrix material of composite materials. Representative hazardous environments include high vacuum, thermal cycling, atomic oxygen (AO), UV radiation, and micrometeoroids and space debris. Among which, atomic oxygen reacts with the surface of polymer materials, causing erosion and critically affecting the lifespan of the structure [1-3]. Methods such as coating the polymer material surface with silicon or metallic materials to prevent material property degradation from exposure to the space environment were proposed. However, coating methods cannot protect the underlying polymer from thermal cycling or penetration of the coating from micrometeoroids and space debris [4-5]. Thus, diverse studies are being conducted to develop polymer materials with inherent resistance against such space environments [6-7]. Among these, a promising method is to fill nanoparticles, which are nonreactive with AO into the resin matrix. The nanocomposite shows a wide range of functionality based on its excellent properties when nanoparticles are incorporated into the polymer-matrix [8-9]. In this study, a silanized nanocarbons, which are an AO inert materials, were added into epoxy resin to increase its resistance to AO attack and to generate compatibility with a polymer matrices. The samples of nanocarbon filled polymer nanocomposites were prepared by the solution blending method. AO exposure and LEO environment synergistic experiments were conducted in the ground simulation systems. The effect of the silanized nanocarbons on the AO resistance of epoxy resin was investigated and the AO resistance mechanism was analyzed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The epoxy resin used in this work was a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F (DGEBF) resin, designated “YDF-170” (Kukdo Chemical, Korea). The curing agent utilized was aromatic amine hardener (4, 4-diamino diphenyl methane, DDM, Kukdo Chemical, Korea). Amino silane coupling agent, 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (3-APTES) with purity of 99%, was obtained from USA Sigma-Aldrich. Distilled water (99.5%, OCI, Korea), acetone (99.5%, OCI, Korea) and ethanol (99.5%, Sigma Aldrich) were of reagent grade. All the reagents were used without further purification. MWCNTS supplied by Iljin Nanotech Co., Ltd, Korea and single layer graphene oxide (GO) powder obtained from Graphene Supermarket, USA were used as the starting materials. The thickness of 1 atomic layer is at least 80%. Distilled water (99.5%, OCI, Korea), acetone (99.5%, OCI, Korea) and ethanol (99.5%, Sigma Aldrich) were of reagent grade. All the reagents were used without further purification.

2.2 Surface modification of fillers

The acid treatment of MWCNTs was a 3:1 (v/v) mixture of concentrated H_2SO_4/HNO_3 (250 ml) for MWCNTs (1.2 g), with ultrasonication at 60 °C for one hour. After the acid treatment, the above mixture was diluted using distilled water through magnetic agitation for one hour, and then filtered, washed to neutral and dried in a vacuum at 70 °C for 24 hour. After chemical oxidation, the silanization of MWCNT was conducted using a methodology that favors silane hydrolysis and condensation on the CNT. 1.0 g of the acid-modified MWCNTs (O-MWCNTs) was dispersed in 2% 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane solution, which was then added to 250 ml of ethanol (240 ml) and water (10 ml). The reaction was conducted while stirring at 70 °C for 4 hours. The silanized CNTs were separated via filtration using distilled water and acetone and were dried at 80 °C for 24 hours. The final product was silane-grafted MWCNTs (S-MWCNTs).

Silanized graphene oxide (S-GO) was conveniently prepared through the following steps. 500.0mg of GO was dispersed in 2% 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane solution, which was then added to 250.0 ml of an ethanol (240 ml) and water (10 ml). The mixture was followed by ultrasonication for 1h and the black and homogeneous mixture was stirred and heated to 75 °C for 12 h. The S-GO were separately by filtration using distilled water and acetone and dried under vacuum at 70 °C for 24 h.

2.3 Preparation of the nanocomposite samples

All the nanocomposites were prepared by the solution mixing method using mechanical/physical approaches to homogeneously disperse the MWCNTs, graphene oxide and their assembly into the polymer matrix. The nanocarbons were dispersed in anhydrous ethanol and sonicated for 30 min. Epoxy resin was added to the nanocarbon suspension. This mixture was heated to 80 °C with magnetic stirring for 2 h to completely evaporate the ethanol. The mixture was placed in a vacuum oven at 80 °C for 2 h to eliminate the entrapped air and remaining ethanol. The curing agent, which was heated to 85 °C to lower the viscosity, was added to the nanocarbon dispersed-epoxy resin and the mixture was stirred for 2 min at 85 °C followed by degassing in a vacuum for 20 min at 70 °C before being cast into the mold. The mold was kept in an oven and the mixture was cured at 90 °C for 2 h, followed by post curing at 150 °C for 4 h.

2.4 LEO space environment simulation facility

The configuration and characteristics of the accelerated ground simulation chamber used to simulate LEO environmental conditions are shown in Fig. 1. The facility can generate four constituents of LEO space environment that is simultaneously applied to verify the synergistic effect of LEO environment on the composite. The vacuum pressure was 2×10^{-6} torr. Thermal cycling (-70 °C to 100 °C) was simulated 14 times over a duration of 20 h. At the same time, specimens were exposed

to UV light during the heating time in order to simulate sun facing and shadow facing. Atomic oxygen was applied to specimens for 20 h to simulate STS-4 conditions. The accumulated flux of atomic oxygen was 4.21×10^{19} atoms/cm².

Figure 1: The configuration and characteristics of LEO environment simulation facility

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 XPS analysis

The characteristics of the MWCNTs modified chemically with acid and 3-APTES were illustrated in Refs. 10. The functionalization of GO nanosheets with 3-APTES was confirmed by XPS spectroscopy. Upon analysis of the wide-range XPS patterns displayed in Fig. 2, two new peaks assigning to Si 2s and Si 2p were observed for S-GO. This confirms the successful attachment of APTES onto the surface of GO nanosheets. The surface atomic concentration of the samples was summarized in Table 1. The atomic percentage of GO sample indicated that impurity at composition of GO existed. From the Table 1, the atom% of Si and N indicated that the siloxane species were grafted onto the surface of GO sheet which confirmed the attachment of APTES molecules to the GO sheet [11].

Figure 2: XPS survey scans of GO and S-GO.

Sample	C (atom%)	O (atom%)	N (atom%)	Si (atom%)	Cl (atom%)	S (atom%)	Ag (atom%)
GO	63.96	32.15	—	—	1.36	2.26	0.28
S-GO	56.96	23.36	8.44	11.24	—	—	—

Table 1: Elemental composition of GO and S-GO.

3.2 Tensile test before LEO aging

Fig. 3 shows the results of uniaxial tensile testing for epoxy composites for a fixed weight fraction (0.5 wt%). Silanized MWCNTs (S-MWCNTs) filled nanocomposites and graphene oxide/S-MWCNTs hybrid filler filled nanocomposites acquired a significant increase in tensile properties compared to the epoxy composites of individual graphene oxide or unmodified MWCNTs.

Figure 3: Tensile properties of nanocarbon filled nanocomposites before LEO aging

3.2 Degradation of nanocomposites under simulated atomic oxygen

The atomic oxygen environment existing in LEO is reported to cause severe damage to polymer materials. The neutral atmosphere of altitude 200km~700km is composed of 80% atomic oxygen and 20% nitrogen molecules. At the altitude of approximately 300km where the International Space Station(ISS) is in operation, the ISS travels at the velocity of around 8km/s so the relative kinetic energy of the atomic oxygen increases to 4~5eV. When impacted with the surface of polymer materials, such high energy atomic oxygen accelerates the rate of surface erosion. In other words, when atomic oxygen impacts the polymer material surface, the organic bonds break, becoming an oxide and separating from the material surface.

However, nanofiller added polymer matrix composites were found to have inherent resistance against atomic oxygen because the added nanofiller has low reactivity to atomic oxygen. In this study, since carbon based nanofillers are not inert against atomic oxygen, silane treatment of the nanocarbon surface was conducted to induce inertness against atomic oxygen and the treated nanocarbon was added to polymer composites in order to investigate the resistance against atomic oxygen attack.

The mass loss of each specimen exposed to the simulated LEO environment was measured to examine the material property change. Factors that can affect the total mass loss include outgassing from the high vacuum and surface erosion from the atomic oxygen and UV radiation. However, in this case, the atomic oxygen induced surface erosion plays the most significant role, thus, the resistance against atomic oxygen attack can be effectively observed.

Fig. 4 shows the mass loss of neat epoxy and nanocarbon filled nanocomposites after the simulated AO exposure process. As can be seen in Fig. 4, AO resistance of the nanocomposites was improved by filling nanoparticles. The reason for the mass loss of the nanocomposites was the erosion of the specimen's surface by AO attack. The silane treated nanocarbon filled nanocomposites had less mass loss than neat epoxy and untreated nanoparticles filled composites. This results indicated that silane treated nanocarbon were less reactive with atomic oxygen than untreated nanocarbon.

This effect can be explained through two mechanisms. The first is the self-healing effect where the atomic oxygen among the hazardous environments causes polymer material surface erosion and reacts with the silicon dispersed within the material before carbon to establish an SiO₂ coating to prevent further surface erosion.

Figure 4: Mass loss of neat epoxy and nanocarbon filled nanocomposites in (a) Only AO exposure and (b) LEO environment synergistic effects.

The second is the difference in the bond energy. Hence, the siloxane bonding of polymer composite with silane treated nanocarbon does not react with the atomic oxygen and this is because of the significantly higher bonding energy compared to the organic bonding (~4eV) of epoxy. Siloxane bonds show resistance against atomic oxygen because the siloxane bonding does not break from atomic oxygen attack as the breaking energy of atomic oxygen (~5eV) is lower than the bond energy of siloxane bonds (~8eV). However, the mass loss of GO filled nanocomposite was found to increase more than that of neat epoxy. This result was due to the acceleration of surface corrosion from the bonding between the atomic oxygen and the GO which has abundant oxygen functional groups. Expediting the oxidation reaction between the atomic oxygen and the GO which has abundant oxygen functional groups, expediting the oxidation reaction a producing volatile oxides. Based on these results, it was found that silane treatment of carbon based nanofillers showed resistance against the space environment especially atomic oxygen attack. Fig. 5 shows the change of tensile strength between the ground and simulated AO conditions for neat epoxy and nanocomposites containing 0.5 wt%. The experimental data are the average values of four specimens. As a result of mass loss mechanical degradation was observed. It can be observed in Fig. 5 that the degradation ratios of the neat epoxy, U-MWCNTs filled nanocomposites, S-MWCNTs filled nanocomposites, GO filled nanocomposites, S-GO filled nanocomposites and GO/S-MWCNTs hybrid filler filled nanocomposites were -5.53%, -3.78%, -2.20%, -5.89%, -4.48% and -3.56%, respectively.

Figure 5: (a) Tensile Strength and (b) Young's Modulus of nanocarbon filled nanocomposites before/after LEO aging.

The tensile strength of the silane treated nanocarbon filled nanocomposites saw less degradation than those of the neat epoxy and untreated nanocarbon filled nanocomposites after LEO exposure. Consequently, S-MWCNTs and hybrid filler filled composites showed the least degradation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The silanization of nanocarbon improved the dispersion of nanocarbon in the matrix and their chemical compatibility with specific polymers for producing nanocarbon filled nanocomposites. The aging experiments showed that the silane functionalization of nanocarbon can relieve the degradation rate of nanocarbon filled nanocomposites against AO attack. Also, this study presented that the AO degradation mechanism of nanocomposites was different for different nanocomposites mainly due to the varying degree of susceptibility of reinforced nanofillers to AO attack.

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